

Growth and Feed Utilization Response of *Clarias gariepinus* to Turmeric and Soursop in Aflatoxin-Contaminated Diets

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Abstract: Fish health, growth, and food safety are all seriously threatened by aflatoxin contamination in aquafeeds, especially in low-resource environments where inappropriate feed storage promotes the growth of fungi. This study assessed the mitigating effects of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) and soursop (*Annona muricata*) on aflatoxin-contaminated feed administered to juvenile *Clarias gariepinus*. A total of eight dietary treatments were formulated, including a control (D1), a mould-contaminated diet (D2 - induced with *Aspergillus flavus*), and six diets (D3 to D8) supplemented with varying levels (20 g/kg, 40 g/kg and 60 g/kg) of turmeric or soursop powders. Growth performance, feed utilization, survival rate, and water quality parameters were evaluated following a 10-week feeding period. Five (5) sample were selected from each treatment. Significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was observed in weight gain (9.30 g), feed intake (10.94 g), feed conversion ratio (1.20), protein efficiency (2.16), and specific growth rate (1.72%/day) in fish fed the mold-contaminated diet without supplementation (D2). However, the inclusion of turmeric and soursop improved these parameters, with optimal results observed at moderate inclusion levels (40 g/kg). Notably, diets supplemented with turmeric produced better feed conversion and palatability than diets supplemented with soursop, which, probably because of its bitterness, exhibited less efficacy at higher concentrations. Every treatment had a 100% survival rate. According to these results, soursop and turmeric may be used to reduce aflatoxin toxicity in catfish diets, providing a sustainable and natural way to improve fish health and aquafeed safety.

Keywords: Aflatoxin, *Clarias gariepinus*, Turmeric, Soursop, Mitigation, Fishfeed.

Introduction

Aquaculture development has raised hopes for food security, particularly in poorer nations. The availability of high-quality feed has been the main obstacle in this development in the agricultural system for decades (Makkar, 2018). Obtaining feed for culture organisms is costly in poor nations like Nigeria, where humans and agricultural animals compete for food ingredients and feed. The farm animals are left with the remnant or decomposing feed materials (Nath et al. 2023). Improper storage conditions of feed ingredients promote fungal contamination. (Guluwa et al., 2023). *Aspergillus flavus*, a fungus known for producing aflatoxins, is a serious global health hazard that pose significant threats to animal health, productivity, and human food safety (Kumar et al., 2017). Aflatoxin contamination of the feed ingredients might be a major quality-reducing factor and depreciator of nutritional value in feed production. This has been reported to affect the growth and he feed utilization of animals. Furthermore, fish or other animals eat aflatoxin-contaminated feed, the toxins cause harm to animals and enter the food chain to the end user with clinical consequences (Oliveira and Vasconcelos, 2020).

Exposure to aflatoxin leads to chronic infection (e.g., abnormal/low growth, low immunity, cancer, etc.) as reported by Bennett and Klich (2013) while acute mycotoxicosis is revealed with its quick manifestation due to exposure to a high concentration of mycotoxin (Williams, et al., 2000). The kind of mycotoxin, the quantity, and the duration of exposure influence the symptoms of mycotoxicosis (Agbon et al., 2013). Sensitivity to the exposure of an organism is also determined by the age, size, genetics, health status, and dietary style of the exposed organism (Bennett and Klich, 2013). They are toxic and their carcinogenic concern has encouraged investigations into their effect on fish (Ellis et al., 2000; Agbon et al., 2013; Ilesanmi and Divine, 2016). Also, aflatoxin which has been reported from research by authors to be responsible for early death, low reproductive function, low growth rate, infertility, and defect in immunity observed in poultry species even at low concentration (Manning, 2001; Sahoo and Mukherjee, 2001).

As the aquaculture industry continues to face feed contamination concerns, scientists are turning to phytochemicals (plant-based additives with therapeutic potential) in quest of cost-effective and natural solutions (Caipang et al., 2019; Tripathi et al., 2025).

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*), which contains the bioactive molecule curcumin (Sharifi-Rad et al., 2020; Zhang and Kitts, 2021), and soursop (*Annona muricata*), which is known for its antioxidant and antibacterial characteristics (Ana et al., 2018; Santos et al., 2023), are two options with promising anti-mycotoxigenic actions. However, scientific information on their efficiency in reducing the harmful effects of aflatoxins in fish diets is lacking.

This study investigates the dietary supplementation of turmeric and soursop in aflatoxin-contaminated feed and their effects on the growth performance, feed utilization, and survival of juvenile *Clarias gariepinus*. The study intends to provide viable and sustainable methods for enhancing fish health and aquafeed safety in low-resource environments where mycotoxin contamination is common by investigating these natural therapies.

Materials and Methods

Experimental site

The experiment was carried out in the Department of Fisheries and Aquaculture, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria. The 10 weeks experiment was carried out in happa net suspended and

stabilized in 2 m x 5 m x 1.5 m concrete pond using synthetic twine to suspend it inside the pond.

Experimental set-up and procedure

The juvenile *C. gariepinus* were obtained from a Sammy farm, Obinze, and acclimatized for one week. The experimental fish were fed with 2 mm Blue Crown® feed of 45% crude protein during the acclimatization period. The experiment was replicated per treatment where ten 12 weeks old juveniles fish (2.59 ± 0.8 g) were distributed randomly in each happa net. The fish were fed at 4% body weight twice daily at 08:00-09:00 hrs and 16:00-17:00 hrs.

Fresh turmeric root was purchased, at the Rumuokoro Market, Rivers State and soursop leaves was plucked in the University (UAES) compound. Both the turmeric and soursop were rinsed with clean water, sun-dried and ground to powder with a locally fabricated hand grinder into powder form before mixing to the feed.

There were 8 treatments that were replicated, that is, Diet 1 (Good-feed/mould-free), Diet 2 (Feed contaminated with *Aspergillus flavus*), Diet 3 (20 g of tumeric/kg of mouldy feed), TRT 4 (40 g of tumeric/kg of mouldy feed), TRT 5 (60 g of tumeric/kg of mouldy feed), TRT 6 (20 g of soursop/kg of

mouldy feed), TRT 7 (40 g of soursop/kg of mouldy feed), TRT 8 (60 g of soursop/kg of mouldy feed). The proximate composition of the ingredients was determined by AOAC (2006) and the details presented in Table 2. The compounded feed was pelletized using a hand pelletizer with a 2 mm diameter and sundried. Weight changes were recorded weekly with a sensitive electronic weighing scale (Meter Toledo FB602) and feed adjusted appropriately. At the end of 10 weeks the effect of these experimental diets were observed.

Growth Performance Parameters and Survival rate

Average fish growth performance was assessed using weight gain, average daily growth, specific growth rate, feed conversion ratio, feed efficiency ratio, and protein efficiency ratio were evaluated to determine the effects of the various treatments.

Average Weight Gain

Final mean weight (g) - Initial mean weight (g) = the average weight gain (g). (Sepahdar *et al.*, 2009).

Daily Growth (DGI)

The daily growth index was calculated as:

$$ADG \text{ (mg)} = \frac{\text{Average Weight gain (mg)}}{\text{Duration of the experiment (days)}}$$

(Hung *et al.*, 1989)

Feed conversion ratio (FCR)

$$\text{Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)} = \frac{\text{Total dry feed fed (g)}}{\text{Total wet weight gain (g)}} \quad (\text{Sepahdar } et al., 2009)$$

Protein-efficiency-ratio (PER)

$$\text{Protein Efficiency Ratio (PER)} = \frac{\text{Wet weight gain (g)}}{\text{Amount of Protein fed (g)}} \quad (\text{Sepahdar } et al., 2009)$$

Specific growth rate (SGR)

Specific growth rate, [SGR (%/day)] = 100 (log W_2 - log W_1) / (T₂-T₁) (Arnanson *et al.* 2009). Where W_1 and W_2 are the weights at time T_1 and T_2 , respectively.

Inclusion of Aspergillus flavus in the formulated feed and determination of aflatoxin

The compounded ingredients was sprinkled with small amount of distilled water to make the feed moist and then mixed with cultured strain of *Aspergillus flavus* from the Microbiology Department, Rivers State University.

The experimental feed was mixed appropriately according to treatment.

The aflatoxin analysis of each feed treatment was done at Nigerian Stored Product Research Institute, Ilorin Laboratory before

the commencement of the experiment with thin-layer chromatography (TLC) (AOAC, 2006).

Preparation of Aspergillus flavus

Sabouraud Dextrose Agar: A 1000 ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 65 grams of Sabouraud Dextrose agar was used to make the medium. This was heated for thirty minutes over a Bunsen burner flame until it boiled and dissolved. The medium was sterilized at 121°C for 15 minutes using the autoclave at 15psi. The medium was allowed to cool down to 45°C and 15ml of the medium was poured into sterile petri dishes. The plates were allowed to set and dried in an oven before used (Merz et al., 1995). The sabouraud dextrose broth, serial dilution, isolation fungi, purification of culture, macroscopic and microscopic examination of fungi isolates, and broth culture were all determined by the Merz et al. (1995) method.

Physico-chemical analysis of culture medium

A daily assessment of temperatures, conductivity, dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, and total dissolved solids (TDS) of the culture medium was done using digital instruments: The RCYAGO® Dissolved

Oxygen Meter (range is 0.0-20mg/L) for DO, JUANJUAN® pH meter for pH, while a meter manufactured by Pakistan Test Instrument was used to measure temperature (range of 0.1-80.0°C and 32.0-176.0°F), conductivity (range of 0-9900 µs/cm) and TDS (range of 0-9999 mg/l).

Table 1 The dietary composition of formulated feed used for the experiment

Ingredient	Feed (Kg)
Maize	22.5
Groundnut cake	30.50
Fishmeal	15.50
Soya-bean meal	30.50
Mineral premix*	0.50
Methionine	0.25
Lysine	0.25
Total	100

*Contains VitA 4000000IU; Vit D. 800000IU; Vit. E 40000 mg; Vit. K3 800 mg; Vit. B1 1000 mg; Vit. B2 6000 mg; Vit. B6 5000 mg; Vit. B12 25 mg; Niacin 6000 mg; Pantothenic acid 20000 mg; Folic acid 200 mg; Folic acid 200 mg; Biotin 8 mg; Manganese 300000 mg; Iron 80000 mg; Zinc 20000 mg; Cobalt 80 mg; Iodine 400 mg; Selenium 40 mg; Choline 800000 mg

Statistical Analysis

The growth and nutrients utilization data growth as well as water quality parameters were subjected to One-Way Analysis of Variance using statistical analysis software (SAS, 1999). Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to evaluate significant averages between treatments at a probability level of 5%.

Results

The concentration of aflatoxin did not have effect on the proximate analysis but the crude fibre seems to be high in the feed with the inclusion of turmeric and soursop especially at the highest level of inclusion. Also the moisture level at the D2 was high compare to others.

Aflatoxin analysis of the experimental feed (A) reflected that feed at the feed mill purchased consist of some levels (4.0919 µg/kg) of total aflatoxin and the feed induced with *Aspergillus flavus* (B) showed

high concentration (190.123 µg/kg) of aflatoxin secreted in the experimental feed. Aflatoxin B1 concentration was the highest in all the samples of the experimental feed analysed while aflatoxin G2 appeared to be the least in terms of the occurrence in the feed. The concentration of total aflatoxin was reduced drastically after the process of pelleting of the experimental feed.

The water parameters observed throughout the experimental period fell within the optimum limits of each. EC ranged between

Table 2 Proximate analysis of the experimental feed samples

Samples	Moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Protein (%)	Lipid (%)	CHO (%)	Fibre (%)
D1	3.15	18.02	38.81	6.1	13.36	20.56
D2	6.17	15.67	39.3	6.1	11.92	20.84
D3	2.67	16.8	39.75	6.5	12.8	21.48
D4	3.82	15.27	39.13	6.3	10.27	25.21
D5	4.47	12.11	38.34	6.2	11.2	27.68
D6	4.87	14.68	39.25	6	12.29	22.91
D7	3.07	15.88	39.13	7.2	9.28	25.44
D8	5.61	11.01	39.25	7.4	8.36	28.37

D1 = Treatment 1; D2 = Treatment 2; D3 = Treatment 3; D4 = Treatment 4; D5 = Treatment 5; D6 = Treatment 6; D7 = Treatment 7, D8 = Treatment 8.

Table 3 Total Aflatoxin analysis of the experimental feed

Parameters	A	B	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8
Aflatoxin G2 (µg/kg)	0.0011	0.1020	0.0008	0.0096	0.0066	0.0076	0.0096	0.0056	0.0056	0.0096
Aflatoxin G1 (µg/kg)	0.0086	0.9800	0.0070	0.119	0.1010	0.1100	0.1130	0.1000	0.0860	0.1040
Aflatoxin B2 (µg/kg)	1.0511	47.4870	0.9110	3.091	3.2850	3.3320	2.9260	3.3380	3.3550	4.1210
Aflatoxin B1 (µg/kg)	3.0311	141.554	2.0311	28.069	26.6670	26.8090	27.6780	26.5960	27.3140	27.7420
Total (µg/kg)	4.0919	190.123	2.9499	31.2886	30.0596	30.2586	30.7266	30.0396	30.7606	31.9766

A = Initial purchased feed, B = Feed spiked with *Aspergillus flavus*,

Table 4 Average water quality parameters in the culture medium

Parameters	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	±SEM
EC (µ/cm)	389.00 ^b	366.33 ^c	376.67 ^{bc}	384.00 ^b	410.67 ^a	416.67 ^a	381.67 ^{bc}	391.33 ^b	80.25
TDS (mg/l)	195.00 ^b	181.67 ^d	188.00 ^c	192.50 ^{bc}	205.00 ^a	203.00 ^a	193.33 ^{bc}	114.67 ^c	12.25
TEMP (°C)	25.43 ^{cd}	27.20 ^a	25.70 ^{bc}	26.07 ^b	25.07 ^{de}	24.70 ^{ef}	24.30 ^f	25.17 ^{cde}	0.11
DO (mg/l)	3.93 ^a	3.83 ^a	3.64 ^a	4.59 ^a	4.10 ^a	4.23 ^a	3.70 ^a	4.50 ^a	0.24
pH	6.96 ^{bcd}	7.12 ^a	6.98 ^{bcd}	7.04 ^{ab}	6.90 ^d	7.03 ^{abc}	6.95 ^{bcd}	6.92 ^{cd}	0.004

EC = Electrical Conductivity, TDS = Total Dissolved Solid, TEMP = Temperature, DO = Dissolved Oxygen, pH = pH.

366.33 µ/cm and 416.67 µ/cm in TD2 and TD6 respectively. TDS values ranged between 188.00 mg/l and 205.00 mg/l in TD3 and TD5 respectively. Also TEMP ranged between 24.30°C and 27.20°C in TD7 and TD2 respectively. But in DO there was no significant difference in its value although the value range from 3.64 mg/l to 4.59 mg/l in TD3 to TD4 respectively. The pH observed were a little around neutral as the values range between 6.90 and 7.12 in TD5 and TD2 respectively.

The initial weight of the experimental feed had no significant difference ($P>0.05$) across the group. But there was a significant difference ($P<0.05$) in the final weight where D1 weight was significantly high (19.28 g) and D2 was the lowest (11.89 g) significantly. This final weight results also reflected in the weight gain where the value of weight gain at D1 (16.53 g) was significantly high ($P<0.05$) than others and D2 had the lowest value (9.30 g). D1, D4, D6 and D7 were not different ($P>0.05$) in the daily growth index but D2 (0.14 mm/day)

was significantly low ($P < 0.05$) compare to others. The experimental fish at the D1 and D6 accepted feed more than any other treatment with an average value of 14.42 g and 14.49 g respectively, making their feed intake significantly different from others with D2 (10.94 g) as the treatment that was significantly low. The feed conversion ratio at D2 (1.20) was significantly high compared to others with D1 (0.87), D4 (0.86) and D5 (0.89) having low value significantly. The protein intake of D5 (6.14) was

significantly ($P < 0.05$) high than others and D2 had low value (4.30) of protein intake. The specific growth rate at D4 (2.42), D5 (2.39) and D8 (2.39) appeared to be significantly higher than others but significantly low at D2 (1.72). The experimental fish throughout the 70 days had 0% mortality making the survival rate to be 100% with no significant difference between them.

Table 5 Growth parameters and survival rate of *C. gariepinus* fed experimental diets

Parameters	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	D8	±SME
Inl wgt (g)	2.75 ^a	2.59 ^a	2.60 ^a	2.51 ^a	2.47 ^a	2.80 ^a	2.57 ^a	2.41 ^a	0.0168
Fnl wgt (g)	19.28 ^a	11.89 ^e	17.07 ^d	18.93 ^b	18.16 ^c	18.94 ^b	18.89 ^b	18.14 ^c	0.1183
WG (g)	16.53 ^a	9.30 ^e	14.47 ^d	16.42 ^b	15.69 ^c	16.14 ^b	16.32 ^b	15.73 ^c	0.1274
DGI (g/day)	0.24 ^a	0.14 ^d	0.21 ^c	0.23 ^a	0.22 ^b	0.23 ^a	0.23 ^a	0.22 ^b	0.0139
FI (g)	14.42 ^a	10.94 ^e	14.20 ^b	14.07 ^c	14.01 ^c	14.49 ^a	14.16 ^b	13.93 ^d	0.0639
FCR	0.87 ^d	1.20 ^a	0.98 ^b	0.86 ^d	0.89 ^c	0.90 ^c	0.87 ^d	0.89 ^c	0.0242
PI	5.60 ^e	4.30 ^g	5.64 ^d	5.51 ^e	6.14 ^a	5.69 ^b	5.54 ^e	5.47 ^f	0.0456
PER	2.96 ^a	2.16 ^d	2.57 ^c	2.99 ^a	2.56 ^c	2.84 ^b	2.95 ^a	2.88 ^b	0.0356
SGR	2.34 ^d	1.72 ^f	2.24 ^e	2.42 ^a	2.39 ^a	2.30 ^c	2.38 ^b	2.39 ^a	0.0312
Survival (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	0.0000

Inl wgt – Initial weight; Fnl wgt – Final weight; WG Gain – Weight gain; DGI – Daily growth index; FI – Feed Intake; FCR – Feed Conversion Ratio; PI – Protein intake; PER – Protein Efficiency ratio; SGR – Specific Growth Rate.

Discussion

Aflatoxin in feed may not be noticed when the feed is physically observed at sight, even

from the result of the proximate analysis done in this research the concentration of aflatoxin present could not be notice. The

moisture contents has been reported (Daramola and Omokpariola, 2025) to be related to the growth of fungal which may be the reason for the increase in the value of most of the diet in the group compared to Diet 1 without the fungi *Aspergillus flavus*. Presence of aflatoxin may not have any effects on the moisture, ash, protein, lipid, carbohydrate and fibre contents of the feed. The increased in the value of crude fibre observed at D5 and D8 may be as a result of the high level of inclusion of the plant extracts (tumeric and soursop).

The outbreak of presence of mycotoxins in the aquatic feed especially aflatoxin was confirm in this study when the feed ingredients bought directly at the agro-allied shop contained level of aflatoxin. This showed that foods or feeds are not safe from the contaminations of aflatoxin which is the most prevalent of all mycotoxin this observation is the same with the report of Daramola and Omokpariola (2025) when animal feed was analyzed from two major feed companies in Jos and Kaduna. Also, this study confirmed the previous findings that presence of fungus *Aspergillus flavus* is responsible for the secretion of aflatoxin (Thakur et al., 2022; Kassaw et al., 2022). Meanwhile, there was a decrease in the concentration of Aflatoxin after the process

of pelleting of the fish feed (experimental feed), this can be related to the report of Ilesanmi et al., (2023) that fish feed production process – grinding, pelleting and drying can reduce the concentration of aflatoxin.

Throughout the experimental period the water parameters were managed in a flow through system in order to avoid error due to water parameters. This may be one of the reason for the 0% mortality rate observed at the end of the experiment. The report of Al-Zaban (2023) explained that an elevation of temperature in an aquatic environment can encourage the growth of *Aspergillus flavus* which can directly spike the production of aflatoxin. This water parameters results of this experiment showed that aflatoxin concentration in feed may not alter any of the water parameters in fish culture under flow through system. This is showing that invasion of mycotoxin in the fish culture may not be easily noticed by regular culture activities/observation. The water quality parameters (temperature, pH, conductivity, dissolved oxygen and total dissolved solid) recorded weekly during the experiment were within the recommendation by the legislation (Boyd, 2003; Davis, 1993; FAO, 2006) so the experimental feed did not have

an influence on zootechnical parameters of juvenile *C. gariepinus*.

The experimental fish were evenly distributed which made the initial weight not to be significantly different from each other. But in the final weight recorded there was no uniformity which may be as a result of the experimental feed. The weight gain which is the difference between the initial and the final weight clarified the impact of the experimental feed on the growth of the *C. gariepinus*. The significant reduction observed in the weight gain of the fish fed with D2 may be as a result of the concentration of the total aflatoxin present in the feed without the inclusion of plant extracts. The observation might be because of aflatoxin contents inside the experimental feed. This observation confirmed the report of low or reduced weight gain stated by Deng *et al.*, (2010) and Anh Tuan *et al.*, (2002) where fingerlings of Nile tilapia were given aflatoxin-B₁ contaminated feed for 20 days, 25 days, and 56 days respectively. In addition, low growth as a result of the presence of aflatoxin in poultry (Popescu *et al.*, 2022; Gelaye, 2024). Likewise, a better weight gain observed at the D4, D6 and D7 might be the presence of the turmeric and soursop in the experimental feed at different inclusion level. In the report of Lee *et al.*,

(2012) where garlic extract was included to the feed of Juvenile *Acipenser ruthenus* there was a demonstration of a notable improvement in weight gain over a 10-week feeding period. In addition, *Clarias gariepinus* given varied amounts of *Allium sativum* to eat in feed showed an overall increase in weight gain (Agbebi *et al.*, 2013). Curcumin, the extract from turmeric can increase the appetite of fish for easy nutrient absorption (Cahyani *et al.*, 2021). This explain the better absorption of nutrients that reflected in the daily growth index which was significantly improved at the D1, D4, D6 and D7 this improvement was better in comparison with the D2. While the reason for the result obtained at D1 might be the low concentration level of total aflatoxin in the diet and inclusion of tumeric and soursop might be the reason of the results obtained for other groups. This can be related to the results of Agbebi *et al.*, (2013) when ginger and garlic was included in the feed of *C. gariepinus*.

The significant reduction in weight gain and DGI notice at the D5 and D8 may be affected by the low feed intake compared to the control group (D1)

It was reported that soursop contains Annonain, the compound called alkaloid which can become bitter and toxic especially

when it is available in large quantity (Harborne, 2014). In relation to this report *C. gariepinus* fed with Diet 8 (the highest inclusion of soursop) had low response to feed intake compared to others with the inclusion of soursop. The higher inclusion might have affected the palatability and increase the bitterness of the feed which affected the acceptability by the fish. The same results was recorded by Kuka and Anayo (2017) when goat was fed with 20% soursop supplemented feed and there was low feed intake. The feed intake was better with the group fed with turmeric than Diet 2. It was reported earlier by Cahyani et al., (2021) that active compound in turmeric called curcumin functions in increasing palatability and appetite stimulant which has direct effect on the weight gain.

The efficiency of the feed can be measured from the feed conversion ratio results, from this experiments tumeric and soursop showed their ability to suppress the effects of aflatoxin on the feed utilization of *C. gariepinus*. The fish fed with D2 has the significantly highest value of FCR. Likewise the protein intake of the *C. gariepinus* fed with D2 has the lowest value of protein intake and PER compare to others.

The increase result of specific growth rate observed in the *C. gariepinus* fed with D4,

D5 and D8 especially indicated that tumeric and soursop can actually be used to mitigate the effects of mycotoxins on the growth rate and nutrients utilization of *C. gariepinus*. Turmeric's essential oil helps decrease excess stomach acid and improve food absorption (Cahyani et al., 2021). In addition, curcumin can improve the fish's immune system. A healthy fish condition leads to increased hunger, which affects its final weight.

C. gariepinus used in this experiment had 100% survival rate which proved that total aflatoxin may not be acute to *C. gariepinus* at the approximate concentration of 25 µg/kg for 70 days. This is contrary to the changes in swimming behaviour and inflammation observed by Farabi et al., (2006) with juvenile *Huso huso* when it was placed on 0.01 mg/kg of aflatoxin B1 for 15 days. Also, Mwihi et al., (2018) observed the swollen abdomen symptom in the rainbow trout fed 0.0018 – 0.0397 mg/kg of aflatoxin B1 and G1.

Conclusion/Recommendation

This study has demonstrated that aflatoxin contamination feed when administered to juvenile *Clarias gariepinus* can impair the growth performance and feed utilization. However, powdered turmeric and soursop

leaves at varying levels of inclusion in the feed showed promising potentials in mitigating aflatoxicosis. Especially, inclusion of moderate levels (40 g/kg) of turmeric or soursop improved WG, SGR and FCR compared to fish fed solely aflatoxin-contaminated diets. Turmeric enhanced feed palatability and nutrient absorption than soursop which may be due to bitterness from its alkaloid content especially at the highest inclusion level.

According to the results, adding natural phyto-genic additives to the diet, such as soursop and turmeric, can be a cost-effective way to lessen the negative effects of mycotoxins in aquafeeds, particularly in environments with limited resources. For wider aquaculture applications, future studies should examine the economic feasibility, immunological reactions, and long-term health effects of these plant-based interventions.

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